

CREATION OF NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The study on neologisms or the new words created in a language has been gaining strength lately and has been getting the attention of linguists. It is obvious that neologisms produce a feeling of curiosity since they frequently appear in the vocabulary of speakers quite suddenly. For this reason, researchers have tried to explain how they are created and have also tried to classify them into different categories, even though they do not always coincide in their approach. While there is a general awareness of the meaning of neologisms that we use daily, researchers have investigated the reasons for their emergence, the preference that speakers show among competing forms of these new words and how they develop. The main aim of this paper is to understand neologisms in English and in the second place to discuss their emergence 208in different areas as a consequence of a number of specific factors and circumstances such as the development of technology and science, news and advertising208and sphere of the Internet. This article discusses neologisms in the English language and how they come about in modern times.

Key words: neologism, word- formation, types of neologisms, new words, technology, advertising, news.

Introduction. Languages are living entities which evolve over time and the lexicon plays a relevant role in this change because while words cease to be used other new words emerge. Neologisms are the new words that speakers create in a language. They serve to keep the language up to-date since they generally emerge because of the new situations that need to be referred to, such as new technologies, new situations in politics and new developments. Speakers create and are exposed to neologisms everywhere, for instance, in the news, social media and advertising. Thus, the study of neologisms is of particular interest because they reflect the language that speakers use to talk about new realities and situations. It could be stated that almost all the words in a language were at some point a neologism.

This paper aims to discuss and analyse the presence of current neologisms in many scenarios of our daily life, with specific reference to English. It defines the concept of neologism, then explains how English neologisms are created, discusses the main areas in which neologisms may be found currently, namely, the fields of technology, science, politics, advertising and the news. Finally, the work analyzes the recent neologisms that have appeared from the several websites, identify their word-formation processes and find out whether affixation is the most used process of forming neologisms.208

Defining neologisms. The word neologism comes from Greek “neo” (new) and “logos” (word). Hence, as its root suggests, a neologism is a new word that has recently been included in the vocabulary of a language [1]. Furthermore, it can also refer to an idiom and an expression that has been incorporated in the speakers’ everyday use of a language. Hence,

“neologisms are new words, word-combinations or fixed phrases that appear in the language due to the development of social life, culture, science and engineering” [2]. Neologisms are opposed to archaisms, that is to say, the expressions that are not used by the standard user anymore or that have been forgotten. Even though archaisms are not commonly used anymore, they must still be present in the dictionary as they can be encountered in texts written centuries ago when these words were used [3].

Generally speaking, when dictionary writers include new words in a dictionary they provide the date in which the neologism was first produced and an explanation about how it was created. When considering whether to include a new word or not, dictionary writers need to take into account the frequency of the neologism in a concrete period of time. The inclusion of neologisms in dictionaries allows speakers to be aware of the existence of these new words [4], after all, neologisms are part of many speakers’ everyday lexicon and their use is increasingly higher nowadays thanks to the media, language contact, the Internet and globalisation. Some experts consider neologisms to be a sign of the normal evolution of language, while others believe that they are a demonstration of how new generations destroy the language. This controversy is also found among speakers who may adopt a different stance on the use of neologisms. For example, some speakers criticise the number of new terms that other people use. Indeed, neologisms — mainly acronyms and borrowings— are commonly associated with colloquial speech or with new ways to communicate such as text messaging, and are therefore not given importance. This controversy can also be seen when talking about technology, a very important area where neologisms are created, as there are “some who argue that the impact of technology has ‘dumbed down’ the language, while there are others who would claim that a language that does not evolve, is a dying language” [5].

Types of Neologisms

Regarding the style, Galperin distinguishes three types of newly coined words. The first one is terminological coinages or terminological neologisms - those which designate new-born notions. The second type is stylistic coinages, - words coined by people who look for expressive statements. The third type is the nonce-words - these words are created only to serve the particular occasion and do not live long [6].

According to Peter Newmark and his book “A Textbook of Translation” there are two existing lexical items with new senses and ten types of neologisms that are classified by their formation. In general he distinguishes twelve types of neologisms. They are:

- Old words with new sense - old words that acquire new meaning; these words usually do not relate to new objects or processes that is why they cannot be connected with technology. For instance a word *revoulement* means ‘return of refugee’; it can be also used for ‘refusal of entry’ and ‘deportation’. In psychology this word denotes ‘repression’. Therefore, it is a loose term, the understanding of which depends on its context.

- Collocations with new meanings - collocations that eventually changed their meanings; the collocations which exist may be cultural as well as non-cultural. There is commonly a recognised translation if the concept is in the Today’s language. In case if the concept does not exist or people are not familiar with it yet, descriptive information has to be given.

- Abbreviation - common type of pseudo-neologisms. The main feature of abbreviation is that we have to pronounce each letter individually.

- Eponyms – any words that were gained from proper names and also brand names (if they were derived from objects) that can be translated only when they are accepted and familiar to the people. When the word, from a proper name, directly refers to the person, we can easily understand and translate it, but if it refers to an object's idea or quality we do not know an extra clarification has to be given in order to understand the meaning.

- Transferred words – words with the meaning that are to a lesser degree dependent on their contexts. They are used more in media or product concepts rather than in technological ones. Furthermore, transferred words may be common to different languages.

- Acronyms – are an expanding common peculiarity of all non-literary texts. They tend to be short and euphonious; acronyms attract our attention and interest in case if we do not know the meaning. So, they make us find out what the letters stand for.

- New coinages – mainly brand or trade names.

- Derived words – new words that are coined by adding one or more affixes to the stem.

- Collocations – are widespread especially in the social sciences and in computer fields.

- Phrasal words – Newmark declares that “phrasal verbs: a) are often more economical than their translation; b) usually occupy the peculiarly English register between ‘informal’ and ‘colloquial’, whilst their translations are more formal. New ‘phrasal words’ are restricted to English's facility in converting verbs to nouns.

- Pseudo- neologisms - Pseudo-neologism is “a generic word stands in for a specific word.

- Internationalisms – borrowed by several languages words that convey concepts which play crucial role in our communication. International words can be found in such fields as science names (e.g. philosophy, biology, mathematics, medicine, lexicology); art (e.g. theatre, music, drama, artist, primadonna); politics (e.g. politics, revolution, communism, progress); technology (e.g. atomic, antibiotic, radio, computer) and so on [7].

The creation of neologisms in English

Most English vocabulary emerges by making new words out of already existing words either by adding affixes or combining words together in order to get compounds. There are a lot of ways of word-formation which are very various and, of course, there are major and minor means of building new words. To quote from the book of lexicology written by G.N. Babich, “Neologisms are mainly coined according to the productive models for word-building in the given languages. Most of the literary coinages are built by means of affixation and word compounding” [8].

The other word-formation processes are: shortening, sound-imitation, clipping, alphabetism, acronyms, back-formation, blending and reduplication. Let us look at main types in more detail in what follows 210

Affixation

Affixation, also referred to as derivation, is a process of word-formation and, therefore, also of morphological neologisms formation which includes coining a new word by adding an affix or several affixes to some root morpheme and is often regarded as the core of English word-formation [9].

Affixes include prefixes, suffixes and infixes. Prefixes occur in front of a root (or a base) and suffixes at the end [10].

As Kate Burridge remarks in English the only things that can be infixed are those expressive words which are used to intensify meaning. All of the seriously offensive intensifiers can be used this way, but there are plenty of neutral-sounding remodellings too like flippin(g), frigging(g), freakin(g) and bloomin(g) as in unbeflippinglybelievable and fanfrigginstastic [11].

Composition

Composition, or as it also referred to, compounding is a type of word-formation which results in forming a fixed combination of two free forms, or words that have an otherwise independent existence, as in frostbite, tape-measure, grass-green [14]. Despite the fact that these items are clearly composed of two elements, they have the identifying characteristics of single words: their constituents may not be separated by other forms, and their order is fixed. If compared with derivation (discussed above) the obvious difference of a derived word from a compound word is that in a former, at least one element, the affix, is a bound form, with no independent existence. Examples: dining-room, blackbird, sunflower, bedroom, bluebell, mother-in-law, good-for-nothing

Shortening or clipping.

Clipping is the word-formation process of shortening words and phrases that does not affect the meaning of the original word. Shortenings or clippings originate from words with two or three syllables and the grammatical function of the new word is the same. Some instances of clipping are “advertisement – ad, telephone – phone, examination – exam, gasoline – gas, gymnasium – gym” [17].

The sources of neologisms nowadays.

All languages change over time and the reasons why neologisms arise are diverse. However, the new developments in technology, economy, politics and other new social contexts that have taken place a very important impact on the creation of neologisms in English and in languages across the world. The new words that have been created are spread more quickly than ever before through the Internet in a globalised world and, knowledge, entertainment and culture are also easily transmitted. New words—and phrases—seem to crop up almost every day. They hang around, and eventually some are formally accepted as mainstream language. Sometimes they are brand new words and other times an old word takes on a new meaning.

Social media and technology have contributed greatly to the formation of new words. Most of these new segments have been named by adding the -tech suffix to a prefix that normally makes reference to the traditional segment of activity they are related to. Although almost self-explanatory, sometimes these terms can be a bit confusing for regular readers. To clear up doubts, here are some examples [18]:

Fintech: Finance + Technology
Proptech: Property + Technology
Insurtech: Insurance + Technology
Wealthtech: Wealth + Technology
Regtech: Regulation + Technology
Legaltech: Legal + Technology
Edtech: Education + Technology
Foodtech: Food + Technology

Biotech: Biology + Technology

There are also such neologisms that have always been actual since their inception.

They are [19]:

- 1.Google: To use an online search engine as the basis for looking up information on the World Wide Web.
- 2.Tweet cred: social standing on Twitter.
- 3.404: Someone who's clueless. From the World Wide Web error message 404 Not Found, meaning that the requested document could not be located.
- 4.Crowdsourcing: The activity of getting a large group of people to contribute to a project or task, especially by using a website where people can make contributions; for example, online proofreading services.
- 5.Spam: Flooding the Internet with many copies of the same message, in an attempt to force the message on people who would not otherwise choose to receive it.
- 6.Geobragging: Repeated status updates noting your location in an attempt to get attention or make other people jealous.
- 7.App: Software application for a smartphone or tablet computer.
- 8.Noob: Someone who is new to an online community or game.
- 9.Troll: An individual who posts inflammatory, rude, and obnoxious comments to an online community.
- 10.Ego surfer: A person who boosts his ego by searching for his own name on Google and other search engines.

It is no use denying the fact that the modern world depends on advertising. Advertising phenomenon is extremely multifaceted and multidimensional. Therefore not surprising that there is a considerable variety of interpretations of the concepts and definitions of the term. The presence of neologisms in advertising where it is important to keep up with new trends is highly remarkable. Amid all processes of creation of neologisms, Mostafa affirms that blending is the most frequent one [20]. Trade workers create words through blending to name products, and then the specialists who carry out the advertising campaigns take advantage of the newness and exclusivity of the neologisms to sound innovative and to catch the consumers' attention.

Conclusion. Taking the received results into consideration, it can be assumed that in today's English combination of different parts of two or more words becomes more popular, in comparison with the neologisms that appeared during the previous decades where the main word-formation processes were affixation and compounding. It should be noted that the present research cannot be considered exhaustive and due to certain limitations it cannot produce any broad generalizations as the number of analysed neologisms is not 212 enough for making comprehensive conclusions. Moreover, some types of coinages such as phrases and collocations were excluded as they did not fit the criteria (only one-word neologisms were analysed by their word-formation structure).

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